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SOUVENIR

**THEME: Latest trends in library tools, technology
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**Karnataka Health Sciences Library Association (KHSLA),
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Smart Literature Search Tools for Researchers: A Review

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Abstract

When deciding on research subjects or analyzing technological trends, researchers should gather and evaluate information from thousands of papers, patents, and technical reports. Information extraction methods from books may assist in speeding up the process. Furthermore, appropriate searching algorithms for the retrieved information are required. While studies into information extraction have been widespread, research into searching and browsing techniques for the retrieved information has not been as appealing. The available published data is enormous; therefore, choosing the appropriate articles, knowledge, and relevant literature related to your field of study is an art. This work proposes an intelligent searching system that includes multiple analytical tools, alternative resources, and paper credibility. We anticipate that researchers will uncover and generate novel research outputs using the suggested searching system.

Keyword: Information Search, Smart Searching Tools, Webstore, Chrome extension, Pull Technology, Push Technology.

1. Introduction

The underlying aim of higher education is to develop good, thoughtful, well-rounded, and creative individuals. In today's world, research and innovation constitute the neo-quantum of the academic strength of a nation. During our research period, most of us must agree that there is an enormous task for the research search and literature review. The literature search is a key element in performing good authentic research and planning of the study. We should have a supercomputer to search and literature review at some point in time. When we talk about research, it is a general perception, and most of us agree that research is searching again and again. Just to generate new knowledge or to find the solution to the problem. However, most of us do not focus upon one primary objective of the research. Research objectives play the research outcome whatever we are getting of them are getting between exiting pool of knowledge.

How to find the solution to a problem, but there is one primary objective of which most of us do not focus upon and then insert objects in space the research of them. Whatever we are getting in between the existing pool of knowledge is the most important objective. Since library professionals deal with the universe of knowledge, we should try to place our research on you to place our knowledge between the existing knowledge. If we train ourselves in that direction, we can guide others also because most of the research that has been carried on is duplicated as it has already been done, and it might be heard about the cases. That data provides what about the field, the data that is being manipulated. So that is not the research objective because a huge amount of the public money is government funds involved in the research process.

2. Objectives of the Study

The literature search is the preliminary activity of the research process. We start searching literature to find the research topics or to find what has been done related to your topic.

- Identify the intelligent technological tools for literature search
- Review the literature search tools
- Suggestion for literature search tools

3. Review of Literature

Several research have backed up the idea of information seeking as a knowledge-building process with several cognitive and emotional phases. Hele-Mai went through the tools that were appraised on the web-based on feature categorization, which considers the tools' overall qualities and their information retrieval capabilities (**Hele-Mai 2001**). According to ongoing study, students in digital contexts go through the same emotional and creative phases of the process (**Branch 2003**). According to Kuhlthau's empirical studies, the Information Search Process is divided into six stages: initiation, selection, exploration, formulation, collection, and presentation, with each stage named after the primary task to be completed at that point in the process. An overview of concept-based information retrieval techniques and software tools currently available as prototypes or commercial products (**Kuhlthau 2004**). According to study,

students' perceptions of the research process have altered as a result of the internet's freely accessible information, in that they expect to discover information fast and without work, and that their subject selection is influenced by an estimate of information availability (**Holliday and Li 2004**). Deadlines often bring the search process to a close. Students' relief at the conclusion of their procedure has more to do with task completion than satisfactory learning results (**Holliday and Li 2004**). Electronic resources were deemed much more vital to students of technology research and study than to students of other disciplines. Few students utilised the library's metasearch engine to find a variety of electronic materials (**Mingder and Chen 2012**). As new smart technologies develop, smart libraries get smarter, boosting their functionality and pleasing their users. Smart library technology has aided in bridging the gap between library services and people's always-changing and conflicting needs (**Gul and Bano 2019**). Students utilise online information resources for academic purposes, and most users are aware of these resources. The majority of users search for information using Google. Most customers utilise internet content to learn and expand their expertise (**Gowridevi 2020**).

4. Information Seeking Technology

Regardless of the search venue, print or digital media, the information search procedure seems to be an overarching process. Students' progress through the information search process is supported and prompted by information retrieval technologies. Timed interventions using an intelligent search increased student outcomes overall, but the retrieval system had issues since not all students went through the procedure at the same rate. Most current information retrieval methods rely on keyword searches, which are ineffective due to their limited accuracy and recall. When it comes to information-seeking technology, there are primarily two types: one is based on the information-seeking process, and the other is based on the information-seeking process.

4.1. Pull Technology

The first technology is pull technology like we have been using google and what we do is we open in google in a web browser and search the information. We try to pull information in the searching engine, so this is the old method.

4.2. Push Technology

Where we have to go to fetch the information from a web site but these days in the era of smart generation, we are searching the technology called push technology where the information that the user is directly delivering as push notification, u no need to visit the website again and again to find information. For example, if we have downloaded the newspaper's dailyhunt, Hindustan news with automatic delivery the notifications are news so push technology. Similarly, google Scholar if you set google scholar alert they no need to search information search again and again what you need to do like you need to add keyword and set the priority like how you want to that information to delivered with give an email id whenever new article published the details of the those article along with the link that is been notified in your email. So we can feel the set of how earlier searching the information we have visit google scholar to search the information now that information has been delivered as notification in your email just like a smartphone. So now the thing is how we can use this push technology in research. Frankly speaking, no full-proof solution has been developed in the library for research to fetch the information. But the thing is that if you see the trend of libraries like in the field of information technology there must be three trends. The first one is like some software solution that has been developed for the library. The second trend is software or technology that has been developed for some other field and we alter and modify the and we use that solution in our library. The third trend is where we work in collaboration with other technologies to implement or customize that solution from the point of view of the library. So, there is no foolproof solution of push technology. We need to do a slide effort to fetch the research information.

5. Literature Search

A literature search is a method of locating a large number of high-quality references on a certain subject by conducting a systematic and well-organized search of previously published material. A

literature search may be done for

a variety of purposes, including gathering information for evidence-based recommendations, as a phase in the research procedure or as part of academic evaluation. The fundamental goal of a comprehensive literature search, on the other hand, is to construct a research topic by analysing the current literature and looking for gaps that may be filled with further study. Whenever we are doing our PhD work or writing a research article, we are faced with a situation like the following.

Figure 1: Literature Search Situation

When we search for a paper, we have been using the keyword of an online database and you find the same 10 or 20 papers. When we read the 10 or 20 papers, you find their reference list and again collect the reference. It might be useful for your research if you collect those papers. Then there will be some papers that have your research supervisor or your collaborative research he might suggest. Then there will be some papers your research supervisors would have been writing, and he or she would ask you to add these papers to your research. In a nutshell, the conclusion is that in your research process, you take your total documents might be sake two for and your paper our readout of PhD and out of reading 107 papers there will be only 5 papers you would have understood it clearly. Lastly, frankly speaking, there will be two papers relevant to your thesis, but if you see your literature review part, we will find a hundred or more than hundred references. So, we are cheating ourselves, we are not doing the actual research. This is the big problem in the literature search, but for the sake of the number we are just adding their reference, but that has not had any relevance to our research.

Developing a Search Strategy

Define your topic

Identify what type of literature looking for

Identify the Sources to Search

Develop Keywords / Search Terms

Think about scope / search restrictions

Design a means of recording what you find

6. Smart Literature Search Tools

Below is the list of some of the best academic search tools that will help get the research material required quickly and easily .

6.1 Google chrome extension: like extensions, we must be aware of the mobile play store where you download apps on your mobile. Similarly, in web browsers, there is a feature of addon on Extension; addon on Extension are small programs or utility it gives a customized web experience. With the help of this Extension, you can create a solution or a web customized web browser with the work on push technology. (1)

Figure 1: Chrome web store

6.2 CORE Discovery: it assists users in locating publicly available versions of scholarly publications. It is supported by CORE's (core.ac.UK) massive collection of millions of full-text open-access publications and information from frequently used third-party services. Discovery cuts down on the time it takes to get complete texts of research articles and the irritation that comes with striking a publisher's barrier. With CORE Discovery, you can be certain that you'll have access to the broadest range of publicly downloadable copies of publications available anywhere on the earth.(2)

Figure 1: Chrome web store

6.3 Mendeley Web Importer: recognizes article IDs on the page you're on and gets metadata and PDF complete texts (where available) for you to add to your library. Importing references and PDFs into your Mendeley Reference Manager collection is simple and quick. Simply click the Mendeley Web Importer extension icon in the toolbar when browsing an article or a list of references in your browser. To store, read, and reference the articles you import, you'll need a Mendeley account. Visit <https://www.mendeley.com> to join up and enjoy 2GB of free storage space.(3)

6.3 Google Scholar Button: This extension adds a browser button to any web page that allows you to quickly visit Google Scholar. To do so, click the Scholar button. Full text may be found on the internet or at your university library. To discover a paper, choose the title on the page you're reading and click the Scholar button. Transfer your online search phrase to Scholar. To view the top three results, press the Scholar button; click "full screen" at the bottom of the popup to see them all. Use widely used citation formats to format your references. Click the quotation button below the result and copy it into your work to view a proper reference. To read or reference the article later, save it to your Scholar library. Click the blue star underneath it or the grey star at the bottom to view all saved articles to save a result.(1)

[Home](#) > [Extensions](#) > [Google Scholar Button](#)

6.4 Lazy Scholar: When you open a scientific document in Lazy Scholar, it looks for a publicly accessible full text. When used, it locates one 36-41% of the time*. NEW: Even if you're not on campus, Lazy Scholar can deep connection with your university to access entire texts. It also tries to extract useful information about the publication, such as fast connections to the population, intervention, results, measures, funding statement, overview, references, abbreviations, and additional papers, if such information is applicable. It also checks for comments on the work in PubPeer, offers multiple citation metrics for the paper and journal, and offers one-click citation styles, including a pre-formatted PowerPoint style.(4)

5.6 Open Access Button: is a browser bookmarklet that notifies users when they encounter a paywall and cannot access an academic publication. Medsin UK and the Right to Research Coalition are both in favour of it. At a BMJ Hack Weekend, a prototype was created. All of the code is publicly accessible on GitHub.(5)

5.7 Open Access Helper: Using unpaywall.org, core.ac.UK, and other resources, you can get lawful open access versions of scholarly journals. Easy legal access to scientific journals in their entirety When you examine a research paper, Open Access Helper recognizes the document's Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and searches the unpaywall.org and core.ac.UK APIs for a link to a lawful open access copy. To view the document, just click the

Open Access Helper badge! Open access is offered at a different place. Green indicates that you should be able to reach this site. Blue: Use the Open Access Button or our Library to make a request.(6)

5.8 Pubpeer: Because most journals do not want to display PubPeer comments on their websites, we designed "browser extensions" to ensure that you never miss a PubPeer remark. The Extension is a few lines of code that checks for PubPeer comments on articles you're reading and displays a banner in your browser if any are found. They are available for all major browsers and can be downloaded here. (7)

[Home](#) > [Extensions](#) > [PubPeer](#)

PubPeer

Offered by: [pubpeer.com](#)

★★★★★ 24 | [Search Tools](#) | 👤 10,000+ users

5.9 Scholarly: Research articles are summarised, interactive flashcards are created, essential points are highlighted, and links to open-access versions of each reference are provided. Scholarly is the

[Home](#) > [Extensions](#) > [Scholarly | Research Paper Summarizer](#)

Scholarly | Research Paper Summarizer

Offered by: [scholarly.com](#)

★★★★★ 22 | [Productivity](#) | 👤 30,000+ users

answer to that stack of papers on your virtual desk - research simplified! This Extension summarises the main ideas of any research paper, report, or chapter in a book. It provides a background reading list for persons new to a field and a linked overview. Do you want to see how a paper builds on earlier work? This is highlighted for you by our new 'Comparative Analysis' engine. Scholarly can help you save up to 70% of the time it takes to extract crucial information from a document for your research and literature review.(8)

5.10 Scholarometer: is a social platform for academic citation analysis that extends Google Scholar. You submit author notes on their disciplines, and our programme

[Home](#) > [Extensions](#) > [Scholarometer](#)

Scholarometer

Offered by: [Scholarometer Indiana University](#)

★★★★★ 2 | [Social & Communication](#) | 👤 1,000+ users

evaluates the effect of an author's works in those areas using this crowdsourced data. Our impact measure may be applied to a variety of sectors. Scholarometer requires the installation of a browser plugin. After installation, the Scholarometer panel will appear in the upper right-hand side of any Google Scholar profile page.(9)

5.11 Sci-Hub X Now: Click the sci-hub "bird" symbol to download the pdf or proceed to the related sci-hub page when on a publisher's website for an academic publication (configure behaviour in "options"). It works by looking for the doi somewhere on the page and then going to the corresponding sci-hub URL. If the sci-hub mirror changes, you may update the sci-hub domain in "preferences"/"options." Each time you click the Extension, it will automatically check whether the server is down and bring you to the settings page to change the domain if it is.(10)

Home > Extensions > Sci-Hub X Now!

Sci-Hub X Now!

Offered by: gchenfc.developer

★★★★★ 52 | Search Tools | 100,000+ users

5.12 Science Research Assistant: is a browser plugin that makes it easier for scientists, journalists, and readers to locate and use current scientific research. While researching and writing your own thesis, finding facts and information as effectively and swiftly as feasible is always a top concern. Its system summarises the content on any web page, emphasizing vital information and offering the most commonly used keywords and phrases. By adding your own rules to the algorithm, you can fine-tune it. This will allow you to swiftly scan any web page for the most relevant information, even large scientific articles that may include a several thousand words or more.(11)

Home > Extensions > Science Research Assistant

Science Research Assistant

Offered by: Science Research Tools

★★★★★ 17 | Productivity | 10,000+ users

5.13 Scite: Users may view how an article has been mentioned and the citation context and

Home > Extensions > Scite

Scite

Offered by: scite.ai

★★★★★ 16 | Productivity | 30,000+ users

categorization using scite. Smart Citations—citations that highlight the context of the citation and identify whether the publication offers supporting or contrasting evidence—help scholars better find and assess scientific literature.(12)

7. Conclusion:

The systematic literature search is an important part of the review process. It comprises conducting a systematic search for studies to generate a transparent study identification report that educates review stakeholders about how studies were discovered and how the review's findings fit within the relevant evidence. The literature search procedure seems to be shared and intelligent tools for information professionals and review teams. Now a days in the era of smart generation, we are searching the technology called smart technology where the information that the user is directly delivering as push notification, they no need to visit the website again and again to find information. Although searching for electronic literature on the internet may be highly valuable, it can also be time consuming and unexpected due to the large number of websites and web pages available, which can lead to information overload and confusion. Current information retrieval technologies must be updated to address the issue of information overload on the internet. To efficiently handle search, retrieval, filtering, and displaying relevant information, much more "intelligence" needs to be included in search tools. Concept-based (or ontology-driven) information retrieval, which is one of the high-impact technologies over the next 10 years, may help with this.

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